

SPATIO-TEMPORAL ANALYSIS OF WATER SURFACE TEMPERATURE IN A RESERVOIR AND ITS RELATION WITH WATER QUALITY IN A CLIMATE CHANGE CONTEXT.

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ABSTRACT

Remote sensing community is making enormous efforts to implement early warning systems capable for following spatio-temporal patterns of water quality and climate change risk indicators, being Horizon 2030 EOXPOSURE project one of them. This work presents first results of surface temperature Landsat 8 Level 2 Collection 2 products analysis for a reservoir and compare them with field data measurements. A Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) of 1.7°C and a Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) of 7% were obtained for these products but validation curve resulted not confident at a 95% level. A semiempirical linear model with 94% accuracy, RMSE of 1.1°C and a MAPE of 5% is presented. It was successfully validated with a control group data set obtaining 94% accuracy. A Water Surface Temperature temporal series is shown for the 2013-2020 period and spatio-temporal patterns are analyzed and discussed. Water surface temperature behavior in zones with algal bloom occurrence present greater significant values, up to 3°C, than those with clearer water, indicating that water emissivity must be revised for these cases.

Index Terms— Water surface temperature, Landsat 8, validation, algal bloom, semiempirical modeling, inland water

1. INTRODUCTION

To ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all is one of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 2030. Water temperature influences most of the physical, chemical and biological properties of water bodies. It also influences human activities such as navigation, aquaculture, and recreation patterns. Global warming may

impose severe risks such as variations in the amount of dissolved oxygen (DO) which may result in water quality deterioration and distortion of an aquatic ecosystem [1]. For aquatic animal health an increasing water temperature may lead to loss or changes in the abundance of species, an increase in the incidence of parasitic diseases, or proliferation of invasive species. It may lead to an increase of algal blooms. In this context, Water Surface Temperature (WST) derived from satellite measurements is a key challenge since it is used as an input in water quality and climate change models.

In this work, we analyze spatio-temporal water surface temperature data derived from LANDSAT 8 – TIRS sensor in an important Argentinean reservoir for the period 2013-2020. This reservoir is the main source of drinking water for Córdoba city, Argentina, which has a population of 1,8 million people. It is an hypereutrophic water body and it has an artificial aeration system installed to mitigate algal bloom occurrences by breaking thermal stratification during Summers [2, 3]. The aim of this work is to propose a valid method to perform accurate water temperature measurements from space and relate them with psychical and biological perturbations which occur in the reservoir. We are also interested in using this data as an input in water quality risk models in the frame of EOXPOSURE project.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1. Study zone, field and satellite data

Figure 1 shows study zone, San Roque reservoir, which presents central coordinates at 31° 22' 56" S and 64° 27' 56" W. It is located approximately 600 meters above sea level in Punilla Valley, a semiarid region in Córdoba province, Argentine. Its drainage area covers 1750 km², receiving the contribution of four tributaries: the San Antonio and Cosquín rivers together with the Los Chorrillos and Las Mojarras

streams, in addition to the small contribution due to the perillage. It has a single emissary, the Suquia River. An artificial aeration system (diffusers lines in blue) were installed in 2008 to mitigate eutrophication.

Field data was collected and generated in the context of a monitoring program carried out by the Ministry of Water, Environment and Public Services of the province of Córdoba (Argentina) [4]. Water surface temperature were measured *in situ* with a Horiba U-22 multiparametric probe at 0.2 m depth. Measurements were carried out at eight stations, shown in black circles in Figure 1, simultaneously with LANDSAT 8 pass during 2013-2020. Three stations are located at the active part of the diffusers. One station at the centre of the lake and four stations near the entrance of the tributaries. Chlorophyll-a concentration were measured on samples extracted at 0.2m depth and sent to laboratory [4]. Atmospheric precipitable water content was obtained from a station located 30km far from the reservoir, named SACO number 87344, from (<http://weather.uwyo.edu/upperair/sounding.html>)

All available LANDSAT-8, Level 2 Collection 2 (L2C2), images for the period 2013-2020 were downloaded from USGS server (<https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/>). L2C2 images include scene-based global Level-2 surface reflectance and surface temperature science products, which have 30m and 100 m spatial resolution respectively [5]. Pixel quality and Surface Temperature quality bands were used to discard images with clouds over the reservoir and a total of 65 images for the period 2013-2020 were used to carry out spatio-temporal study. In order to obtain Surface Temperature (ST) in °C, Band 10 is re scaled according to equation (1), in which the constant term includes the re scale parameter and the difference from Kelvin to Centigrade grade (149 - 273.15).

$$ST = B10 * 0.00341802 - 124.15 \quad (1)$$

An image from 22/02/2017 in which an algal bloom was registered were use to calculate a chlorophyll-a map. A semiempirical model validated for San Roque Reservoir was used, equation (2) [6], where NDVI is the Normalized Vegetation Differential Index calculated as $(B4-B5)/(B5+B4)$, and Chl-a is Chlorophyll-a concentration in mg/m^3 .

$$Chl - a = 236.31 * NDVI + 124.45 \quad (2)$$

Land was masked using the date of 15-12-2020 which presented the lowest reservoir level.

2.2. Water temperature surface modeling

For modeling and validation purposes, we used temperature field data measured during days with no clouds: 09/10/2013, 13/01/2014, 05/03/2015, 08/05/2015, 17/08/2017, 21/11/2017 and 15/12/2020. We obtained a set of 48 pairs field-satellite data. Garganta pairs were removed from data set since this station is located in a narrow part of the reservoir and contributes with noise for satellite analysis purposes. Root mean

square error (RMSE) and Mean Absolute Percentual Error (MAPE) were calculated in R platform with Metrics package [7]. Linear regression was performed to evaluate ST product by analyzing significance of slope and intercept confident interval values. If slope confident values include 1 and intercept confident values include 0, then the measurement method is trusty. Otherwise, it cannot be used to monitor the variable. Linear regression was also used to develop a semiempirical model of Water Surface Temperature from field data set. For this purpose, 65% of the data (31 pairs) were used as training group and the rest 35% (17 pairs) were used as a control group to validate the algorithm. RMSE, MAPE and determination coefficient (R^2) were used to evaluate its performance. Confidence intervals of slope and intercept, (R^2), RMSE and MAPE were used to evaluate validation curve.

Fig. 1. San Roque reservoir with screening samples in circles, diffusers lines in blue, main neighbor cities in squares, tributaries and outfall. Inset map correspond to Argentina

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Water Surface Temperature Modeling

Table 1 presents RMSE and MAPE calculated between field and ST L2C2 product for each date (7 pairs of data per each). Atmospheric water vapour content is also included in the table since it is an ancillary data for atmospheric correction. RMSEs from 0.6°C to 3.4°C and mean absolute MAPES from 4% to 13% can be seen. It is worth noting that the date with the greatest errors, 05-03-2015, is the one which presents the highest atmospheric water content. Total RMSE and MAPE are 1.7°C and 7% respectively. Recently, Bonansea et al. found lower errors in Rio Tercero reservoir, Argentine, who obtained 0.94°C [8]. A linear regression was done between satellite and field data and R^2 equal 0.93 with $p < 0.001$ was obtained. However, it presents a slope equal to 0.84 (95% confidence interval 0.77 to 0.91) and an intercept equal to

2.57 (95% confidence interval 0.99 to 4.13). An analysis of confidence intervals indicates that it does not correspond to a model with slope 1 and intercept 0, which is required to validate a method.

Table 1. Precipitable water content, RMSE and MAPE calculated between ST L2 C2 and temperature measured in situ.

Date	H ₂ O (mm)	RMSE	MAPE
09-10-2013	19.4	1.5	0.09
13-01-2014	13.6	1.3	0.05
05-03-2015	34.4	3.4	0.13
08-05-2015	15.9	1.4	0.07
17-08-2017	19.4	0.6	0.04
21-11-2017	16.1	1.6	0.07
All Dates	–	1.7	0.07

Equation (3) presents the semiempirical lineal model obtained from the training data set.

$$WST = ST * 0.85 + 2.38 \quad (3)$$

This model shows an accuracy of 0.94 (R^2), a significant p-value < 0.0001 , a root mean square error (RMSE) of 1.1°C and a MAPE equal to 5%. These results are according to previous studies performed with LANDSAT 5-TM on the same reservoir [2] and match better with references results discussed above. The validation curve performed with the control data set presents a R^2 equal to 0.93, and RMSE equal to 1.3, an MAPE equal to 5%, showing a good fit. It showed an slope equal to 0.96 (95% Confidence interval 0.82 to 1.1) and an intercept equal 0.26 (95% Confidence interval -3.00 to 3.51). Analyzing slope and intercept confidence intervals, it can be seen that the validation curve is significantly equal to $x=y$ function, indicating that the method is valid and trusty to measure the variable with a 95% confidence level.

3.2. Spatio-Temporal Analysis

Figure 2 presents Temporal series of WST derived over Centro station. Black dots correspond to retrieved satellite data and red dots to in situ measurements. Solid line is a lineal interpolation over black dots.

It can be seen that this variable shows a periodic behaviour, showing peaks in Summer and valleys in Winter, with high thermal amplitude (20°C average). The series presents a mean of 19.4°C, a median of 19.3°C, a maximum of 29.1°C and a minimum of 10.9°C. It can also be seen that 2017 year shows warmest WST registered (29°C) which coincides with a Niña event and a dry period.

Figure 3 left column presents Mean, Maximum and Minimum temperature maps calculated over the whole temporal series for San Roque Reservoir during Summer Season, while right column shows analogous information for Winter Season. It can be observed that expected mean values

Fig. 2. Temporal series of WST derived over Centro station for 2013-2020 period. Retrieved satellite data (black dots), in situ data (red dots), and linear interpolation (solid line).

for Summer range mainly between 25.3 and 26.2°C while in Winter they range between 13.5 and 13.9°C. From spatial distribution data it is possible to observe in Summer the effect of artificial aeration systems on Zona A and Zona B stations (East region), which impacts on decreasing temperature due to thermal stratification rupture. The same pattern was observed from LANDSAT 5-TM data [2]. In the case of Maximum Summer maps, temperature ranges mainly between 27.6 and 29.4°C while in Winter it ranges between 15.8 and 16.7°C. In this case, spatial patterns are very different, showing high values over for Summer over North, South and Center-West regions and lower ones over diffusers zones and Center-North region. This behaviour is not easy to understand by analyzing only physical aspects, since cool water entrance from rivers should cause a decrease in water temperature. In contrast, warming effects on river entrances is observed coinciding with regions of high algal bloom occurrence [2].

Figure 4 shows a Landsat 8 RGB (432) image, a temperature and chlorophyll-a concentration map of San Roque reservoir corresponding to 22-02-2017, in which a big algal bloom can be observed. It is worth to noting that temperature map spatial pattern is identical to its analogous Chlorophyll-a map. A statistic analysis was performed over bloom and no blooms regions, considering a threshold of 150 g/L in Chlorophyll-a concentration to define it. We obtained average values of $(30.2 \pm 0.5)^\circ\text{C}$ and $(27.1 \pm 0.1)^\circ\text{C}$ for bloom and no bloom regions respectively. The T-test performed over both groups indicates that means are not significantly equals, $p < 0.001$. This issue is very important since changes in modeled temperature could be associated with changes in emissivity of water due to high amount of algae presence. For ST retrieval, a water emissivity near 0.9885 is used and it is considered constant for the whole water body [9]. Buettner et al. have carried out laboratory emissivity measurements for different surfaces in the region of 8-12, where Band 10 from TIRS is included [10]. They found the following average values regarding wa-

Fig. 3. (left) Mean, Maximum and Minimum temperature maps calculated over the whole temporal series during Summer Season. (right) Analogous for Winter Season.

ter systems: 0.993 (pure water), 0.972 (water plus thin film of petroleum oil), 0.966 (water plus thin film of corn oil), 0.961 (water plus a thin film of polyethylene).

Fig. 4. RGB Landast 8 OLI (left), Water Surface Temperature (middle) and Chlorophyll-a (right) images for a Bloom event occurred in San Roque reservoir on 22/02/2017.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Water surface temperature derived from satellite measurements is a key challenge since it is used as an input in water quality and climate change models. This study presents novel validation results of Surface Temperature LANDSAT 8 L2 C2 products recently released by USGS Earth Explorer platform.

Field data set was used to evaluate their performance at the study zone. However, validation curve against in situ data did not show accurate results. It could be noticed that a semiempirical modeling is a good approach to make up for this issue since we have obtained 94% accuracy, a RMSE of 1.1 and a MAPE of 5%. A temporal series of Water Surface Temperature could be built for the period 2013-2020 and spatial-temporal patterns could be studied. Zones with high level of algal biomass, detected as high amount of chlorophyll-a concentration, present temperatures significantly different from those with no blooms by + 3°C. More studies should be done in this direction in order to evaluate water emissivity influence and chlorophyll-a - temperature relationship.

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